

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL TRAINING OF ATHLETES USING PSYCHOLOGICAL METHODS.

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Annotasiya .

Maqolada zamonaviy sport sportchilarning texnik va taktik tayyorgarligiga yuqori talablar qo'yishi muammosi ta'kidlangan, bu esa o'z navbatida o'yin texnikasini o'rganish jarayonini takomillashtirish uchun psixologik vositalarni izlash zaruratini tug'diradi.

Annotation.

The article highlights the problem that modern sport places high demands on the technical and tactical training of athletes, which in turn creates the need to search for psychological means to improve the learning process of playing techniques.

Kalit so'zlar: taktika, texnika, mashg'ulot, samaradorlik, psixologiya.

Key words: tactics, technique, training, effectiveness, psychology.

Introduction. Preparation of an athlete of any sport specialization is a fundamental principle. Physical fitness is the basis for achieving load standards, and the athlete's psychological state is a statistical construct that ensures the correct, desired fulfillment of the specified load standards.

Competitive sports activities are characterized by the need to perform complex technical actions under time pressure and significant physical and psychological stress. Therefore, the process of teaching technical and tactical techniques to players at the initial stage, based on the sequence of mastering game techniques, must include psychological tools that facilitate these actions.

Many experts [1, 2, 3] in the field of physical education and sports point out that without improving the initial training system for the athletic reserve, it is impossible to achieve consistent success in high-level team competitions.

Research objective: to improve the technical and tactical preparedness of athletes.

Object of study: technical and tactical training of athletes.

Subject of study: psychological tools in the process of technical and tactical training of athletes.

The hypothesis of the study is that the use of psychological tools will improve the process of teaching game techniques to athletes-players at the initial training stage, which in turn will increase the level of technical training of athletes.

Discussion of Results. Our analysis of scientific and methodological literature to identify modern psychological tools proposed by experts for implementation in sports practice led us to focus on ideomotor training. Ideomotor training is mental training. There is a connection between thought and movement—the thought of it triggers the movement itself.

The mechanism of ideomotor training for technique development is that when a movement is mentally imagined, the central nervous system sends impulses to the periphery, and intramuscular receptors respond to these impulses similarly to real actions. Repeatedly passing through these channels, nerve impulses accumulate sensations of movement in the muscles and develop intramuscular memory, which is retained in the body for a long time. Using ideomotor training before practicing new or complex techniques can significantly reduce the time required to master them. Ideomotor training can also be used to reinforce positive experiences by mentally recording your most successfully executed movement.

Ideomotor training is, to a certain extent, programming one's own brain. Using this technique, a person mentally imagines the ideal execution of their exercise, and the depth of immersion in this mental image determines the success of the training session or performance in a real-life competition. A subtle connection with the subconscious is established.

Four basic mechanisms of the ideomotor act can be identified: 1. Preliminary perception of movement and the associated excitation of kinesthetic cells; 2. The emergence of a motor image and the associated excitation, similar to that which occurred during perception; 3. Excitation in motor cells, arising from their temporary connections with kinesthetic cells;

4. Transfer of excitation to the muscle and the responsive working reaction [4]. Ideomotor training is based on a mental process – representation. An athlete's technical skill largely depends on their ability to utilize the laws governing the mental process – representation. The main ones are the following:

1. The more precise the mental image of a movement, the more precise and "pure" the movement performed.

2. Only a representation in which the mental image of the movement is linked to the athlete's muscular-articular sense is considered ideomotor. Athletes often rely solely on visual representations, which are ineffective. When an athlete uses ideomotor thinking, allowing the image of the movement to "pass through themselves," micro-contractions and micro-relaxations are quite clearly visible in their muscles.

3. The impact of mental representations is significantly increased when they are expressed in precise verbal formulations. One should not simply imagine the movement, but simultaneously verbalize its essence silently or in a whisper.

4. When learning a new element, imagine performing it at a slow tempo. You can then alternate between slow and fast speeds.

5. When mastering a new element, it's best to mentally imagine it in a position that's close to the actual position. Exercise equipment is very helpful here.

6. During ideomotor imagery of a movement, it sometimes occurs so strongly and clearly that the athlete begins to move involuntarily, indicating the establishment of an associative connection.

7. It's incorrect to think about the end result immediately before performing an exercise. In this case, concern for the result takes precedence over how to achieve it.

If an athlete can vividly and clearly imagine a movement, they will most often be able to execute the technique correctly on their first attempts. As they gain ideomotor training skills, athletes are encouraged to practice it not only in a calm environment or relaxed state, but also in the presence of external distractions. It is advisable to begin training with simple movements, gradually moving on to more complex coordination elements. By mastering ideomotor training, athletes can find their own technique for creating clear mental images. Visual learners may find it easier to observe the movement sideways, as if on a screen, while kinesthetic learners may find it easier to feel themselves in motion. For training, you can suggest completing the following tasks: imagine the technique in slow motion, feel the gradual activation of muscles, imagine the most energy-efficient version of the technical element, concentrating on the working muscles and releasing unnecessary tension in other muscle groups, imagine the movement as a whole at the fastest possible tempo, etc. After repeatedly mentally replaying a technical action, the execution of the technique turns out to be much more effective. As experience in sports practice shows, the use of ideomotor training allows one to significantly reduce the number of repetitions of a

technique when practicing in sports classes, reduce the time it takes to master it and improve the coordination characteristics of technical actions [5, 8].

A key condition for effective mental training is comparing your physical muscle-motor sensations with the results of actual motor actions. By repeatedly practicing the movements in different situations, they will become automatic.

Ideomotor training not only helps you master the technique of a particular movement, but also significantly improves your muscular endurance and athletic performance, and helps you maintain the technique of complex exercises after a break in training.

An analysis of scientific and methodological literature contains indications from some researchers that it is recommended to learn the ability to think through motor actions after the energetic part of the training or at the end of the lesson [6, 7].

A pedagogical formative experiment aimed at improving the movement learning process included the following.

Psychological and pedagogical tools were incorporated into the training sessions, which were held three times a week: at the beginning of the main part (5 to 10 minutes), athletes mastered the technique of creating ideomotor images. In total, elements of ideomotor training were used during 24 training sessions throughout the experiment.

Before introducing ideomotor training techniques, discussions were held with the athletes:

The first discussion

was aimed at developing the athletes' understanding of "What is ideomotor training?", "What is it used for?", and "The principles of executing ideomotor representations."

The second discussion was held midway through the session to identify "What difficulties were encountered when using ideomotor training?" After the discussion, conclusions were drawn and, based on these, adjustments were made to the ideomotor training process.

The third discussion concluded the session, discussing the results of using ideomotor representations: "Did you like ideomotor training?", "Will you use it in the future?"

Since ideomotor imagery is based on the ability to create clear mental images and focus internal attention on them while in a reduced psycho-emotional state, the athletes spent the first three sessions mastering relaxation techniques. These sessions were conducted before the training process, accompanied by

specially selected musical accompaniment that promoted relaxation and muscle relaxation. While mastering the relaxation technique, the participants were advised to visualize their mental images clearly and vividly, with essential kinesthetic sensations.

Next, we began mastering the technology of ideomotor representations of the technical skills required by the training sessions planned for mastering them.

Our initial goal was to implant in the athletes' minds an extremely precise mental image of the desired movement using any available means and methods. This involved using video recordings of correctly executed elements of sports technique, as well as an athlete capable of demonstrating high-quality execution of the technique, and, of course, a demonstration of the movement technique by the coach himself.

The technique for learning a technical element was aimed at initially imagining its execution, first at a slower pace, and then at a faster one.

Athletes who had difficulty mastering movement technique were given additional training in the form of homework.

In the second half of the experiment, the performance of ideomotor imagery became more challenging. Specifically, the athletes had to take turns creating ideomotor imagery in the context of the training process and the accompanying noises. Specifically, one athlete was tasked with creating ideomotor imagery of the movement being mastered during a given session, while the remaining athletes continued training as usual. This was done to ensure that the athletes adapted to performing the movement in any conditions.

The technical fitness results of the athletes in the experimental and control groups after the pedagogical experiment were analyzed as follows.

At the end of the pedagogical experiment, final testing was conducted to determine the effectiveness of using ideomotor training in technical training.

When assessing the technical fitness of the athletes in the control and experimental groups, the following was revealed, respectively:

- technical errors: in the "speed dribbling, including hitting" test, 55% and 56% of them made frequently encountered errors: inability to dribble without visual control, incorrect dribbling (carrying, holding the ball during turns, transfers), dribbling in front of the player (instead of in front and to the side);

- "passing the ball in motion" – 39% and 39% of errors, including not fully straightening the arms at the elbows, lack of accompanying movement after releasing the ball from the hands, and inaccuracy in passing; – In the "distance throws" test, 46% and 47% of errors were identified, with the most common

being: the throwing arm not fully straightening at the elbow, no sweeping, accompanying wrist movement, rushing the throw and no follow-through during the release of the ball, no aiming before the throw, head down;

- "free throws" - 34% and 35% errors, throws at the hoop with too low (or high) a trajectory, use of the supporting arm in the throw, elbows flared out to the sides during the throw.

Based on the results of an analysis of scientific and methodological literature, the following psychological and pedagogical tools were included in the set of tools for improving the technical training of athletes during the pedagogical experiment: conversations, relaxation psychotechniques, and ideomotor training.

Findings and conclusion. The formative pedagogical experiment confirmed the effectiveness of ideomotor training in the technical training of athletes in the initial training groups. When determining the technical fitness of athletes in the control and experimental groups, reliable differences were found after the experiment in the following tests:

in the "speed dribbling, including hitting" test - 33.3 - 55%, 29.3 - 49%;

- in the "distance throws" test - 13.6 - 45%, 11.0 - 37%;

- "penalty throws" - 10.2 - 34%, 7.7 - 26%. No significant differences were found in the "passing the ball in motion" test scores between the control and experimental groups after the educational experiment (13.1% - 36%, 12.9% - 36%).

During the experiment, athletes in the experimental group made fewer errors, which is significantly lower than that of athletes in the control group, confirming the effectiveness of psychological tools in technical training.

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